

– the text of the program should consist of separate modules, ensure minimal costs in the further development of the system and its transfer to other server platforms.

Based on the objectives of the project, it is necessary that the database supports the "client-server" technology, it is assumed that the designed information system will distribute functions between at least the client and the server, i.e. part of the functions of the application program will be performed on the "client", and the other part on the "server".

Conclusion

Thus, this project includes the latest achievements in the field of computer technology. Their use enables the user to obtain the necessary data from the database located on the server as efficiently and quickly as possible.

Currently, a pilot version of the data bank of technologies and innovative projects has been developed. The use of the proposed software product provides:

- 1) the ability to use the application, both in local and global Internet networks;
- 2) limited access to the system (user rights - only viewing data; administrator rights - viewing and changing (editing) data);

3) viewing and changing the database (adding new innovative projects to the database, deleting projects, editing project data);

4) search for an innovative project by a given value, namely, by the code of an innovative project;

5) selection of a set of innovative projects according to specified criteria, namely, the selection of projects is carried out according to specified criteria values such as payback period, investment volume, sales volume.

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MODERN APPROACHES TO THE ORGANIZATION OF QUALITY INCREASE IN THE BEAUTY AND COMMERCIAL MEDICINE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This article reveals the problems of improving the activities of beauty industry companies. The article examines the strengths and opportunities that make up the strategic potential of a companies in beauty and commercial industry sector.

Keywords: beauty industry, innovative methods, process innovation, salon business

The beauty industry for the Kazakhstan market of services is quite a young direction. The current socio-economic situation and widespread socio-cultural values in the country significantly contribute to the development of the beauty services market. An organization that has entered this market should regularly carry out industry and strategic analysis of the external environment, since growing markets are always attractive for new business entities.

It is often difficult for the client to justify their dissatisfaction, and it is economically unprofitable for the master to recognize the defects of the service, so there are significantly fewer complaints in the documentation of the beauty industry company than upset visitors. The lack of customer feedback makes it difficult for enterprises to manage the quality of services provided and "disables" the competition mechanism. There are many companies in the beauty industry, and the consumer has to look for " their " master, who provides a high-quality service, for years, demonstrating their unsuccessful experience in the

most prominent place (Ennis & Harrington, 1999). Competition is a complex process, and companies must prove their leadership in the field of beauty almost daily, constantly working on the level of their service and the quality of services provided.

The beauty studio as an object of promotion in the market is a very specific structure. Salon business is a complex type of service, because it involves a lot of qualified specialists, including those from the medical field. Due to the fact that the salon business market is currently on the rise, the services they provide are extremely popular. The beauty industry is a complex, highly competitive business, so an employee working with clients must be not only beautiful, but also smart, have strong communication skills, as well as managerial abilities that allow you to effectively organize the work of many specialists, manage customer records, and resolve possible conflict situations (Chen & Popovich, 2003).

The analysis of modern problems and trends in the activities of organizations, as well as the peculiarities

of their interaction with the external and internal environment, showed that the tightening of competition in the market of beauty services shifts the focus in the activities to the development of measures to improve the internal environment. The research and development of innovative methods is engaged in innovation science - a field of knowledge that covers the issues of methodology and organization of innovation activities, a significant place among the problems of which, which have become the subject and object of its research, is occupied by a relatively independent field of knowledge-social innovation (Hurley, 2004). These are new means of regulating and developing social processes that can meet the complexity of the social situation, aimed at meeting the needs of a person and society in conditions of high uncertainty of circumstances.

The introduction of a new product is defined as a radical product innovation, if it concerns a product whose intended application, functional characteristics, properties, structural or used materials and components significantly differ from previously produced products. Technological innovations are the final result of innovative activity, embodied in the form of a new or improved product or service introduced in the market, a new or improved process or method of production (transfer) of services used in practice. In industry and the service sector, there are two types of technological innovations - product and process. In industry, product innovation encompasses the introduction of technologically new or improved products (Afthinos, Theodorakis & Nassis, 2005).

Such innovations can be based on new technologies or on a combination of existing technologies in their new application. Technological improvement of a product affects an existing product, the quality or cost characteristics of which have been improved by using more components that are efficient and materials, or by partially changing one or a number of technical subsystems.

Process innovation is the development of technologically new or significantly improved production methods, including methods of product transfer. Innovations of this type can be based on the use of new production equipment, new methods of organizing the production process or their combination, as well as on the use of research and development results. Such innovations are aimed at improving production efficiency, but may also be intended for the production and delivery of technologically new or improved products that cannot be produced or delivered using conventional production methods.

To introduce technological innovations in the beauty industry, of course, you need to take into account the experience of introduction to traditional markets. At the same time, it is always necessary to analyze competitors and the market as a whole (Afthinos, Theodorakis & Nassis, 2005).

However, introduction of new technological tools in order to strengthen quality management in a company it is necessary to implement change management systems. In most cases, it goes in a positive relation with personnel demotivation factors. Ignoring this as-

pect can lead to usefulness of introduction of new technologies and standards. To increase motivation to work, you can offer the following activities:

- attract employees and encourage their participation in exhibitions, master classes and trainings;
- organize seminars for regular customers based on the salon and involve artisans in their conduct;
- improve the system of material incentives for quality work, through a system of bonuses and bonuses;
- develop a system of moral incentives: the introduction of the title "employee of the month", annual certification for quality work, introduction to the practice of corporate events.

The masters who come to work in the salon have different levels of qualification. Some seek to improve it on their own by attending courses and seminars. For a number of masters, this option is not acceptable due to the lack of free funds. In order to improve the level of qualification of masters, it is advisable to introduce on a permanent basis in-house training, which could be carried out by the most qualified employees and employees who have received external training at the expense of the enterprise (Johnston, 2004). It will always be relevant for employees to participate in external seminars and trainings conducted by leading industry specialists to master new technologies of the beauty industry with the subsequent introduction of new services in the salon, as well as to improve the skills of new specialists.

An important issue is the development of a quality management system. In matters of management, the most competent in the enterprise of the beauty industry is the head himself. He also needs to master the basic methods and techniques of quality management of services, to study the experience of similar successful organizations, since today customer satisfaction directly affects the amount of profit of the enterprise. Therefore, in order to attract customers, the tasks of the head of a hair salon can be as follows::

- develop and implement a quality management system based on the application of recognized quality systems and the requirements of international standards, including a system of personnel training and motivation, a system of relationships with consumers and suppliers;
- to achieve a level of quality of services that meets the expectations of the consumer and allows for their voluntary certification;
- maintain the functioning of the quality management system at a high level.

Manager of a company in beauty industry in most cases assess all risks by himself and is more motivated rather than people work in a company (Lagrosen & Lagrosen, 2005). However, that risks can influence decision that manager does. That is why it is strongly important to manager develop his own skills in quality management and assess new technology advantages in order to strengthen client service. Quality management in Kazakhstan and introduction of new technologies is still developing sector of study. It is necessary to provide deep quantitative studies on quality management systems of beauty and commercial medicine sector.

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